

NOR-Flash Memories under Protons and Neutrons

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Abstract—Commercial NOR-Flash memories were written with several patterns at different bias voltages and irradiated with protons and neutrons in order to know the effect of the bias voltage on the single event cross sections. No conclusive related results were found, but weird single event functional interrupts were observed.

Index Terms—NOR Flash, neutrons, protons, single events.

I. INTRODUCTION

THERE is a clear interest of the space community on the behavior of flash memories under radiation, and many works have been done trying to understand the expected phenomena (e.g. [1] and references therein). Classically, flash memories are categorized into two well-defined groups: NAND and NOR memories. Both consist in a very large array of floating-gate transistors, the main difference between both being the way that they are interconnected. Each architecture offers different advantages and drawbacks. In particular, NOR memories are more expensive, with less capacity than NAND Flash, and slow to write, but the good functioning of all cells is guaranteed, so no error correction codes (ECC) are necessary, and fast and random access to any specific word is possible. These characteristics have made NOR Flash interesting for blocks that must be seldom or never rewritten, and often read. For example, firmware and bootloaders, software storage in microcontrollers, calibration tables for sensors, etc.

It is well known that bias voltage can affect the sensitivity of memories against single events. For example, cross sections of single event upsets (SEUs) in static random access memories (SRAMs) strongly depend on this parameter [2]. This relation also comes up in single event transients (SETs) [3], in single event latch-ups (SELs) [4], etc. Therefore, it is relevant to verify if the bias voltage affects the performance of the flash memories (namely, NOR Flash devices), taking into

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TABLE I
SELECTED MODELS. SIZE IS EXPRESSED IN MEGABITS. ALL THE DEVICES ARE ORGANIZED IN 8-BIT WORDS AND 256-BYTES PAGES.

Model	Manufact.	Size	Tech.	Code
IS25LP032D-JNLE		32		ISA
IS25LP016D-JNLA3-TR	ISSI	16	65	ISB
IS25LP128F-JBLE		128		ISC
W25Q16JLSNIG	Winbond	16	58	WBA
W25Q128JVSQ		128		WBB
S25FL127SABMFI103	Infineon	128	65	INA
S25FL128LAGMFI013		128		INB
SST26VF080AT-104I	Microchip	8	—	MCA
		Mb	nm	

account that the physical phenomena required to erase and write the memories make use of high voltages coming from charge pumping circuits, with an output value more or less proportional to the applied bias voltage [5].

The initial objective of this paper is to verify if the bias voltage that was used to write on NOR-flash memories has a significant influence on the occurrence of single events when these devices were exposed to radiation. A collection of samples of models from several companies was written at different bias voltages, followed by irradiations with protons and neutrons in different facilities.

II. TEST SETUP

First of all, it is necessary to indicate that a cell is erased if the charge in the inner floating gate is completely removed, and is written (or programmed, using the accepted terminology) if electrons are injected in the floating gate. In NOR-Flash memories, erased cells are interpreted as “1”, and programmed cells as “0”.

A. Characterization of devices

A set of different NOR-Flash memories from several manufacturers, listed in Table I, were selected for the tests. Public information about these devices can be found on [6]–[13]. Some manufacturers use proprietary fabrication processes with specific names, such as MirrorBit by Infineon, SuperFlash by Microchip [14], etc. The INA device includes error-correction codes (ECC) to remove single bit upsets. Besides, the MCA model requires a preliminary disabling of the software writing protection following the instructions by the manufacturer. Another characteristic of this model is that the structure of the cells is slightly different from a classic floating-gate one, this dramatically reducing the erasing time.

TABLE II
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PACKAGES FOR THE DIFFERENT MODELS.

Model	Code	Package	A2
IS25LP032D-JNLE	ISA	SOIC-8 150 mil	2.65
IS25LP016D-JNLA3-TR	ISB	SOIC-8 150 mil	1.75
IS25LP128F-JBLE	ISC	SOIC-8 208 mil	2.16
W25Q16JLSNIG	WBA	SOIC-8 150 mil	1.55
W25Q128JVSIQ	WBB	SOIC-8 208 mil	1.95
S25FL127SABMFI103	INA	SOIC-8 208 mil	1.80
S25FL128LAGMFI013	INB	SOIC-8 208 mil	2.3
SST26VF080AT-104I	MCA	SOIC-8 150 mil	1.85
			mm

As the devices were not decapsulated, it is necessary to provide information about the packages. All the samples have SOIC-8, with widths of 150 mil (3.81 mm) or 208 mil (5.28 mm). Also, the vertical thickness of the plastic coating changed among models. Both parameters are shown in Table II, taking into account that the standard name for the vertical thickness is *A2* for all the manufacturers.

They were checked and written before the irradiations using a tester based on a STM32 Nucleo-L432KC development board, which could change the bias voltage for the memories with a 12-bit DAC followed by a common-emitter output stage. As the memories were supposed to work at lower voltages than the nominal output values of the microcontroller, all the I/O signals crossed some commercial level shifter to adapt the logic levels. The samples were mounted on a small printed circuit board that could be easily plugged on the tester. All the devices had Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) communication and worked in page write & page read modes, which were selected for this experiment. SPI clock frequency was set to 1.6 MHz and, in the case of observing a possible bitflip, the clock frequency was reduced to 50 kHz and the full page read twice more and the three possible values voted in order to discard that the observed bitflip was provoked by a spontaneous glitch during the reading process. Fig. 1 shows the procedure to verify the samples and prepare them for the tests. This procedure included tests to verify that any possible value could be efficiently written in the device. The procedure of erasing the memory was simplified as: 1) sending a specific instruction 2) waiting for the maximum chip erase time¹ to elapse. There were three possible values of bias voltage: 3.3 V, lowest nominal bias voltage (LNBV) according to the manufacturer's instructions, and lowest experimental bias voltage (LEBV). The latter value was measured by setting the bias voltage at a value under the LNBV value, erasing the memory, verifying that the both 0x55 & 0xAA patterns could be written in all the addresses and correctly read later. In each step, the value of the bias voltage decreased 100 mV and the process repeated until the memory failed. Table III shows the values of the bias voltages according to the manufacturer and as measured by the researchers.

During the irradiations, all the pins of the devices were grounded, as suggested in other experiments [1] and, once

Fig. 1. Preparation of samples before the irradiation. In some circumstances (e.g., writing 0x55 at 3.3 V), not all the steps were necessary. In the case of failure, the test-up system had to be checked to identify and fix possible failures.

TABLE III
LOWEST BIAS VOLTAGE: NOMINAL ACCORDING TO MANUFACTURERS (LNBV) AND EXPERIMENTAL (LEBV). ALL THE VALUES ARE EXPRESSED IN VOLTS.

Code	LNBV	LEBV	Code	LNBV	LEBV
ISA	2.3	2.1	INA	2.7	2.5
ISB	2.3	—	INB	2.7	2.2
ISC	2.3	2.1	WBA	2.7	2.3
MCA	2.3	1.6	WBB	2.7	—

the samples were deactivated and its handling safe, they were sent back to the laboratory and its content read in the same conditions as it was written looking for possible disagreements.

B. Radiation facilities

Proton tests were performed in October 2023 at the Nuclear Physics Institute of the Czech Academy of Sciences (Prague, Czech Republic), where a cyclotron U-120M provided 10^9 15-MeV protons/cm² to irradiate every sample. Neutron campaigns were performed in February 2024 at ENEA (Frascati, Italy), where the samples received 10^9 14-MeV neutrons/cm² obtained from typical D-T reactions. The reason of choosing these energy value and fluence was based on the results presented in [1]. Despite the fact of testing NAND Flash memories, this paper reports the strange dependence of the cross sections on the proton energy, which grows or decreases depending on the model, so we expected this energy values would increase the chances of observing single events. The use of both facilities was granted by the RADNEXT project [15].

SRIM [16], [17] shows that the typical penetration depth of 15-MeV protons in plastic (namely, epoxy) is 2.18 mm, although it can be slightly different if other chemicals are included to improve mechanical and thermal properties. That allows the protons to reach the silicon die of all the models, usually placed below a plastic layer not thicker than $0.5 \cdot A2$ (0.8–1.3 mm from Table II). However, the effective LET in the

¹This parameter is provided by the manufacturer

TABLE IV
IRRADIATIONS AT CAS WITH PROTONS

Code	0×00			0×55			0×FF
	3.3V	LNBV	LEBV	3.3V	LNBV	LEBV	3.3V
ISA	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
ISB				x	x		x
ISC	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
INA	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
INB	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
WBA				x	x		x
WBB	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
MCA							

TABLE V
IRRADIATIONS AT ENEA WITH NEUTRONS

Code	0×55		
	3.3V	LNBV	LEBV
ISA	x	x	x
ISB			
ISC	x	x	
INA	x	x	x
INB	x	x	x
WBA			
WBB	x	x	x
MCA	x	x	x

sensitive regions differs from model to model. On average, SRIM predicts that the energy loss for protons is around $0.38 \text{ MeV}\cdot\text{cm}^2/\text{mg}$ per $100 \mu\text{m}$ of plastic (epoxy) package at the top plastic surface.

Tables IV & V show the different samples that were irradiated in both facilities. One can see that the number of samples ranges from 2 to 7, the most samples found in the largest and most advanced memories. Besides, the consistency of the experiment required that every sample of each model belonged to the same batch. Finally, it is necessary to say that some models were tested in only one facility.

Concerning the potential displacement damage, the equivalence factors are 1.79 and 3.38 1-MeV neutron/cm² for 14-MeV neutrons and 15-MeV protons respectively [18]. Let us also bear in mind that the energy loss while crossing the upper plastic layer will make these value lower, depending on the plastic width. Calculations done with SRIM [16], [17] indicate that the total ionizing dose induced by the protons is around 410 rads (Si). That induced by neutrons is negligible.

III. RESULTS

A. 15-MeV protons

The first striking conclusion from the tests is that neither single event upsets nor single event functional interrupts (SEFI) were observed after the proton irradiations. Assuming that the generation of single events follows a Poisson's distribution, the upper threshold values for cross sections must be lower than $2.9 \cdot 10^{-15}/N \text{ cm}^2/\text{bit}$, N being the size in megabytes,

with 95-% confidence. In the case of the largest memories, this threshold becomes $2.23 \cdot 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2/\text{bit}$. Obviously, no dependence on the bias voltage could be found.

Besides, all the devices were fully operative after the irradiation. Thus, they could be fully erased and later programmed without any malfunction in the process, which was done at the nominal voltage, 3.3 V.

B. 14-MeV neutrons

Due to the unavailability of samples of some models, not all of the models tested in the first campaign could be tested under neutrons, although a model from Microchip was ready for this test. Surprisingly, even if all the devices passed the proton tests, many of them showed some kind of failures after the neutron irradiation. As we will see, these failures seem not to be SEUs and probably fall in the category of SEFIs.

Models labeled as ISA, WBB, INA and INB did not show bitflips and the stored information could be successfully read after the tests. Thresholds for single event upset cross sections are identical to those shown in the previous section. On the contrary, other models underwent several problems at the time of reading them back:

- **ISC:** namely, the model written at the lowest bias voltage according to the manufacturer. From the #595 page on, the information read in many pages is different from the initial content. The characteristics of the bitflips point to some kind of single event functional interrupt. For example, bitflips are grouped in large clusters inside a specific page, although not all the cells of the page are affected. Typically, all the corrupted words changed from 0×55 into 0×00; sometimes, there are subclusters of corrupted words (around 10-12) where only one or two bits have changed from 1 to 0. And the most interesting fact is that the errors seem to vanish if the memory is read again. This fact suggest that the transient biasing required to read the device is removing failures from the internal blocks.
- **MCA:** two samples of this device (biased at 3.3 V and LEBV) presented an interesting SEFI, since the whole content of the first page was set to 0×00. Unlike the previous devices, successive reads of the device cast identical behavior.

The following step was to find out if the devices were still operative and that could be erased and programmed.

All the samples except one could be successfully erased after the neutron irradiation. The only exception was the INB device programmed at the manufacturer's lowest bias voltage, which required a second erasing round to carry out the removal of the stored charge. This suggest that the irradiation made the erasing less efficient, taking longer than the manufacturer specifications.

After erasing the content at the bias voltage of 3.3 V, the devices were programmed again writing the 0×00 pattern in all the words of the memory. This process was successful in most of the devices, with the exception of the two MCA samples that showed SEFIs immediately after the irradiation. In this case, the full content of several pages among the twenty

initial ones was $0 \times FF$ instead of 0×00 , even though most of the memory had been correctly programmed.

IV. DISCUSSION

As it was stated in the introduction, the main purpose of these experiments was to find out if the bias voltage at the time of programming played a major role when the NOR-Flash was exposed to radiation. In our opinion, results are inconclusive, since those memories with anomalous behavior had been programmed at any of the possible voltages. At any rate, it is possible to conclude that bias voltage is not a concern at least to the proton fluences reached in this paper.

An interesting outcome from the test is that the ISA, INA and WBB passed the tests, so they are good candidates to be used in space systems, although additional tests should be performed using other kinds of radiation.

Another interesting feature is that neutron radiation seems to be more harmful than protons. None of 41 samples irradiated with protons showed failures of any sort, whereas four samples out of 18 irradiated with neutrons did despite the fact of sharing fluence and energy values. One may argue that samples from Microchip were not irradiated with protons and that its behavior in this circumstances is unknown, but other two models clearly failed under neutrons but passed the proton tests.

Obviously, this damage cannot originate in total ionizing dose, since it is well known that protons cause this kind of damage and neutrons do not, so we would have observed exactly the opposite behavior (more failures after proton irradiation). Displacement damage must be discarded according to [18], since the induced damage by protons is almost twice than that of neutrons, as explained in Section II-B. A possible way to explain this strange behavior is to investigate how the incident particles interact with matter and the secondary ions released after electromagnetic and nuclear reactions.

Figs. 2 and 3 show the secondary particles issued from simulating a simple silicon structure with G4SEE [19] exposed to 15-MeV protons and 14-MeV neutrons. In the case of proton irradiation, daughter particles are generally electrons or slowed protons, with some recoil silicon nuclei. On the contrary, nuclear reaction caused by neutrons are more interesting. One can see that, besides silicon, other species can be found. In particular, it is interesting the production of alpha particles with peak energy around 6 MeV and with a high ionizing power. This fact would explain the tolerance of the NOR-Flash memories to proton, but the occurrence of failures after the neutron irradiation.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Proton and neutron tests have shown that some models of commercial NOR Flash memories are good candidates to be used in some radiation environments, although more specific tests with radiation emulating that present on the target system should be done. Apparently, SEUs do not appear neither in 15-MeV protons nor in 14-MeV neutrons, although some devices show different kinds of SEFIs after the neutron tests. This behavior could be linked to the emission of secondary

Fig. 2. Secondary particles generated in silicon by 15-MeV protons vs. kinetic energy. Electrons with energy below 250 keV are out of scale. Very rare daughter particles have been removed for simplicity.

Fig. 3. Secondary particles generated in silicon by 14-MeV neutrons vs. kinetic energy. Very rare daughter particles have been removed for simplicity.

particles. Finally, the existence of dependence between single event cross sections and bias voltage could not be answered, since the results are inconclusive, given the fact that the only events were SEFIs of which no statistical study could be done.

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